

**IMPACT OF NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020
ON RURAL PRIMARY EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT**

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Introduction:

The New Education Policy announced by the Ministry of Human Resource Development aims at transforming the Indian education system to meet the needs of the 21st century. It aims at making the education system holistic, flexible, multidisciplinary, aligned to the needs of the 21st century and the 2030 Sustainable Development goals. Even though there is a need to think whether the villages in India will cope with all the reformation of education system through NEP2020. India is the country of villages. It has of about six lack villages. It is supposed that the villages in India are still striving to develop and avail all the modern facilities. The New Education Policy has adopted 5+3+3+4 model for school education. It would help the child for formative years at early stage of life. As par the provisions in NEP 2020 the digitalization, multilingual and the like approaches cannot be implemented as it is. Just we need to think of the questions regarding the villages. What about the schools where the students don't go in them? There are schools but they don't have their own buildings. What about the schools where we find only one teacher? What about the village which don't have schools in them.

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Objective of Study:

- 1) To study whether the NEP is significant in rural context
- 2) To study about how the NEP can be useful to develop rural area education
- 3) To study whether the NEP can stop or lower down the dropout rate of the students.
- 4) To study how NEP can attract the students to schools.

Hypothesis:

- 1) The NEP 2020 does not fulfill the rural area education development requirement
- 2) The NEP 2020 fails to impart world class education to the students in far remote villages.

Early childhood Care Education:

Early childhood care education begins with *Anganwadis*. The *Anganwadis* workers are trying their hard to impart education to the children in a play way method. They are also taking care of the children in *Anganwadis* with motherly love but *Anganwadi* workers are already burdened with numerous public health and nutrition duties. In this pandemic situation they have played a vital role of doing surveys in rural area. If the same situation persists they may get engaged

in the tasks other than teaching and taking care of the children. They should be given training for six month diploma course for child care and it isn't an easy task. Over 10 Lakh vacancies are still open at school level. What about the facilities provided to the *Anganwadis*? Let's have a look at one of the facilities. Figures from December 2019 show that over 3 lakh *Anganwadis* centers don't have proper toilets and over 1.5 lakh lack potable drinking water. The facilities mentioned above are the basic needs for the children. They should be provided to the children with proper way and condition so that the children may enjoy learning in *Anganwadis*. Most of the time the *Anganwadi* teacher goes for survey and the class goes without teacher. In this condition how can NEP2020 reach its goal of quality Early Childhood Care Education.

Digitalization and Distance Education:

India is a country of the villages and the villages are away from the cities where no proper electricity and internet connectivity are available in the remote areas we cannot find proper connectivity so regular phone call is not possible, leave about the video call or video conference. Now-a-days online classes are going on but the students from the remote area are not able to attend such classes due to the less connectivity or no internet coverage area. As per UDISE only 9.85% of government schools have functional computers and 4.09% have internet connections. In such situations how can we achieve the goal of digitalization and distance education. The area where connectivity of internet is available, blended learning is possible. But what about the areas which situate in the heart of darkness.

NEP 2020 Recommends spending of 6% of GDP on Education:

In his article 'does the National Education Policy miss out on real issues?' Gourav Vallabh says "The NEP recommends a spending of 6% of GDP on education. However, spending on education has fallen from 4.14% in 2014-15 to 3.2% in 2020-21 under BJP Regime. Even this amount may get cut down by 40% owing to the corona virus pandemic in the current year bringing the education spending to just 2% of the total budget. There is hence no clarity on whether the NEP proposes financing of 6% of GDP to come from public funds or private investments.

Now let's have a look on how much is spent on education in USA and in India. This statistics is of the year 2013. Public Education in the United States (Education policy on Ballotpedia) gives the numbers. 'In 2013 the united states had 49,77,1118 students enrolled in a total of 98,454 schools in 18,093 schools districts. There were 3109,101 teachers in the public schools. There was roughly one teacher for every 16 students. There was roughly one administrator for every 295 students. The average amount of spending for every pupil was \$ 10,700 in 2013 and average graduation rate was 81.4 percent.

The condition in India is so much different in the same aspect. Financial Express published an article of Prachi Gupta 'How much it takes to educate people in India on November 28,2019. It says 'the raising cost in education has made it extremely cumbersome for financially weak families in India to let their children pursue studies. The condition of Indian Education is dismal with more people in recent times not even making it to school, according to recent report by NSO about 70% of rural Indians are not able to complete their SSC. This stands at over 40% for urban India. In Higher Education, only 1 in every 10 Indians has graduate degree and above. Pursuing a college degree in general courses means average expenditure of Rs. 5,240 per student in rural areas and more than three times the rural average spends i.e. 16,308 in urban areas.

If all the above information is taken into consideration, we shall easily jump to the conclusion that there would be no change in the situation in coming years when the NEP 2020 is going to be implemented. If we think our country is

going to be the supreme power in the world, we have to be ready to increase the expenditure on education like USA does. The NEP 2020 doesn't give any hint of spending amount on Education as the developed countries do.

Knowledge and jobs:

There is a mismatch between the knowledge and the job. The skills imparted through the NEP will be of local area. As there is a chance to the students to choose the skill based learning, the students will choose the skill of the family occupation. They will be skillful in the same skill. The students whose family doesn't have any occupation of their own, they will be unable to choose the right option. There is one more threat and that is if the students get the skill of the local occupation, they won't get a chance to seek job in the global scenario. This may give a chance to strengthen caste system and discrimination on the basis of occupation.

Multilingualism and the power of Language:

NEP 2020 says "Wherever possible, the medium of instruction until at least Grade 5, but preferable till 8 and beyond, will be the home language/mother tongue/local language/regional language. Thereafter, the home /local language shall continue to be taught as a language wherever possible". It shows the emphasis given on the local language. The students will be masters in local language but what about the global language English? In 4.17 and 4.19 the NEP again gives the emphasis on Sanskrit. It says "Sanskrit will thus be offered at all levels of schools and higher education an important enriching option for students, including as an option in the three language formula.. it further says Sanskrit textbooks at the foundational and middle school level maybe written in Simple Standard Sanskrit (SSS) to teach Sanskrit through Sanskrit (STS) and make its study truly enjoyable. About English and other foreign languages will also be offered at the secondary level for students to learn about the cultures of the world and to enrich their global knowledge and mobility according to their own interest and aspiration." If the students are asked to choose the language of their own interest, no doubt they would prefer the primary language and Sanskrit or their mother tongue. They will not give preference to the secondary language. Mother tongue or local language and Sanskrit will have limited scope in the global scenario. The point (4.17) mentioned above shows that policy makers have given much scope to Sanskrit. It shows they have poured their love on Sanskrit lavishly. English language is supposed to be the window of knowledge of the world. If most of the students prefer their mother tongue as the medium of their education, the researcher thinks that they would stay away from the knowledge of the world and there would be no English Language Learners (ELLs) in rural area. So it can be said the NEP 2020 to give the world class knowledge to the students from rural area.

Dropout rate of the Students:

The dropout rate of the students is a major problem the NEP 2020 has to face. The dropout rate is greater and the policy doesn't have any provision to cease it. Gourav Vallabh, National spokesperson, congress and Professor of Finance gives an evidence in 'NEP will add to the existing rural-urban divide that has caused great damage to the marginalized.' He says "An oxford report revealed that 75% of the 6 million children currently out of school belong to socially marginalized communities (32% Dalits, 25.7 % Muslims and 16.4 % Tribals) except for Kerala, Punjab and Sikkim,. The quality of infrastructure in the country is inferior in rural areas. Along with this there is another problem in India and that is child labor. The policy cares for ECCE and the formative development of a child but the child labor problem eludes. So NEP 2020 wont be able to fulfill the requirements for rural area education and development.

Suggestions:

- 1) Basic facilities for *Anganwadis*

- 2) Lessen down the burden of other works from *Anganwadi* workers and primary teachers.
- 3) A parallel system of health worker and survey.
- 4) Blended learning in the village areas.
- 5) Brick-and-mortar education.
- 6) Strengthening of Internet connectivity in villages
- 7) Opportunities for developing hidden potential of the students.
- 8) Increase expenditure on education
- 9) Scope for English language.
- 10) Making of magnate schools / theme schools.
- 11) Making of charter schools.

Conclusion:

In primary view the New Education Policy 2020 seems to be good but the closest in the closest look one can find so many shortcomings and weaknesses of the policy. The policy can be successful when the government provides the villages all the facilities that cities possess. The facilities like internet connectivity and electricity are the basic needs for digitalization and distance education. The socially marginalized students, the child labor and the out of school students are to be taken in the main stream of education. Then and then only we can dream of India to be the supreme power in the world.

References:

- The article based on 'A Long Road on the National Education Policy 2020, published in The Hindu on 31/07/2020
- The article – NEP will add to the existing rural – urban divide that has caused great damage to the marginalized: published in The Indian Express updated: September 6,2020 by Gaurav Pathanaia
- The article 'Does the National Education Policy miss out on real issues?' Published in the New Indian Express.' By Gourav Vallabh on 12 August 2020.
- How much it takes to educate people in India; cost of education revealed in four charts. Published in Financial Express by Prachi Gupta on November 28,2019
- वामन मेश्राम : अनुवादक डी. आर. ओहोळ मराठा- कुणबी – ओबीसी आरक्षणाचा तिढा (समस्या) राष्ट्रव्यापी आंदोलनाशिवाय सुटणार नाही प्रकाशन मुलनिवासी पब्लिकेशन ट्रस्ट. सर्व्हे नं 54301 केशव नगर मुंढावा पुणे -411036 पान. 109.
- National Education Policy 2020 – Ministry of HRDC, Govt. of India. Page No- 7, 11, 14,
- Public Education in United States (Education Policy on ballotapedia.org)